

SUBWAVELENGTH WAVE PROPAGATION CONTROL BY USING ACTIVE ELASTIC METAMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Elastic metamaterials have been extensively investigated due to their unique abilities on controlling propagation of subwavelength elastic waves. One of the most interesting properties is the generation of band gaps, in which elastic waves cannot propagate through. The growing technological development in electro/magneto-mechanical couplings of smart materials introduces controlling degree of freedom for passive elastic metamaterials. The new concept could allow fine control of the material physical behavior to induce tunable properties that cannot introduced by the passive approaches. In the study, active elastic metamaterials with shunted piezoelectric materials and electrorheological elastomers are suggested. The theoretical analysis and numerical validation of the active metamaterials with detailed microstructures will be presented for designing adaptive applications in band gap and extraordinary waveguide. Active elastic metamaterials could provide a new design methodology for adaptive wave filters, high signal-to-noise sensors and structural health monitoring.

1 INTRODUCTION

Constant research for advanced design techniques in electromagnetics, acoustics and elasticity such as the coordinate transformation method triggered the development of multifunctional engineered composite materials, called metamaterials [1-12]. The focus of metamaterials is on the extreme range of characteristic material parameters, including negative values, high anisotropy and exceeding gradient, due to their specific microstructure design. The realization of the acoustic/elastic metamaterial (EMM) permitted capabilities of low-frequency sound/vibration attenuation, negative refraction and acoustic/elastic lenses to control sound/elastic waves. Therefore, metamaterials extended significantly the spectrum for material selection and paved a new way for subwavelength wave propagation control. However, passive EMMs have limitations in real-time wave propagation control, which are mainly caused by frequency-dependent effective material parameters resulted from the locally resonant mechanism. The band gap from the current EMM design is fixed and limited to a narrow frequency band. Real-time geometrical adjustments of the resonator system will be extremely difficult and unacceptable in practice applications. Constant technological material revolution in electro/magneto-mechanical coupling provides a new choice in the development of active metamaterials. Full integration of adaptive materials, electronics, computing resources and power systems with passive metamaterials can form a hybrid active metamaterial system, whose material properties can be digitally and remotely controlled.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to piezoelectric materials in active and/or passive vibration control applications. As a promising passive technology, piezoelectric shunts were widely adopted for mitigating structure flexible vibrations and absorbing sound energies [13-22]. In the passive shunt design, only external circuit elements were directly connected to the electrodes of the piezoelectric patch, where the energy generated by the piezoelectric patch induced by the host structure is consumed within the external circuit. With the shutting approach, the incident signal can be sensed simultaneously by the piezoelectric material and the use of a passive network guarantees the stability of the coupled system. Specifically, it has been experimentally demonstrated that the elasticity of piezoelectric materials shunted with negative capacitance circuits can be electrically tuned independent with frequency [23,24]. Based on this merit property, periodic arrays of negative capacitance shunted piezoelectric patches were demonstrated numerically by employing transfer matrix method to control

the band gaps of phononic beams [25]. By observing the link between shunted piezoelectric materials and periodically engineered phononic crystals and EMMs, several successful designs have been demonstrated for 1D and 2D plate flexural wave attenuation by using locally resonant shunts [26-29]. Both numerical and experimental results showed that waves can be efficiently damped near the circuit resonant frequency and the tunability of wave band gap frequencies can be virtualized by circuit impedance adjustment. It is believed that the shunted piezoelectric material is one of promising candidate selections for in design of active EMMs.

Magnetorheological/electrorheological (MR/ER) elastomer is another kind of prospective smart materials in vibration and sound attenuation applications with shear modulus being controlled rapidly, continuously, and reversibly by applying an external magnetic/electric field [30-32]. Recently, MR/ER elastomer that overbears sealing and environmental contamination problems in MR/ER fluid applications attracts special attention in the areas of tuned vibration absorbers and isolators. Based on a simple mass-spring system, Liao et al. developed an ON-OFF control algorithm and designed a tunable isolator with MR elastomer [33]. The experimental results show that the responses of the payload are suppressed significantly in comparison to a passive system. By discovering the relation between the phase advance of relative acceleration and natural frequency of the primary system, a stiffness tuning algorithm is proposed for MR elastomer dynamic vibration absorbers [34]. Numerical simulations and experimental results demonstrate that the designed MR elastomer vibration absorber are highly adaptive in real-time control and the excitation frequency can be rapidly tracked. In elastic wave control applications, MR elastomers were integrated into a multi-layered one dimensional phononic crystal to actively tune wave band gaps [35]. Due to the similarity of ER and MR elastomers, several vibration and wave control applications have also been found with ER elastomers [36-38]. For instance, a tunable band structure of locally resonant phononic crystals was investigated by applying various electric fields upon ER elastomers embedded in an elastic matrix [38]. MR/ER elastomers would be another kind of attractive materials in active EMM applications.

In this paper, we numerically demonstrate two types of active EMMs for subwavelength wave propagation control. In the first part, an active mass-in-mass lattice system with the negative capacitance piezoelectric shunting is studied to indicate the flexible band gap control. This promising application is then demonstrated with an active EMM plate for bending waves. The second part deals with design and physical realization of a flexural waveguide and a focal lens based on active EMMs composed with ER elastomers. The numerical simulation is conducted to show tunability and flexibility of the proposed waveguide and lens over a broad frequency range, various steering directions and different focal point locations without altering the microstructures.

2 BAND GAP CONTROL IN AN ACTIVE EMM PLATE WITH SHUNTED PIEZOELECTRIC PATCHES

A frequency regime around the resonance frequency, also called a band gap, was observed in EMMs, in which waves cannot propagate through and is trapped in the resonators. In this part, the wave band gap will be demonstrated to be tuned by a negative capacitance piezoelectric shunting in EMMs.

2.1 Negative capacitance piezoelectric shunting

Now consider a thin shunted piezoelectric patch operated in transverse modes and connected to a parallel negative capacitance $-C_n$. It is readily found that the shunted system is equivalent to a ‘simple’ transducer with a lower capacitance. According to Hagood and von Flotow, modified effective Young’s modulus of the shunted patch can be expressed according to the following expression as [14,39]

$$E_p^{SU} = E_p^E \frac{C_p^T - C_n}{C_p^T (1 - k_{31}^2) - C_n} \quad (1)$$

where $k_{31} = d_{31} / \sqrt{s_{11}^E \epsilon_{33}^T}$ denotes the electro-mechanical coupling coefficient with ϵ_{33}^T , d_{31} and s_{11}^E being the dielectric constant at constant stress, piezoelectric constant, compliance of the piezoelectric patch at constant electric field, respectively, E_p^E is Young’s modulus of the piezoelectric material when

the shunting network is in a short circuit configuration, C_p^T is the electrical capacitance of the piezoelectric material at constant stress.

A significant result from Eq. (1) is that the shunting system has the ability to modify elastic properties, and thus may be used to control the dynamic behavior of the piezoelectric material. Figure 1 shows the normalized effective modulus $E_{eff}^* = E_p^{SU} / E_p^D$ of PZT-5H in function of the negative capacitance ratio (NCR), which is defined as $\lambda = -\frac{C_n}{C_p}$. It can be found that the normalized effective stiffness modulus is equal to the short circuit stiffness for large values of λ and equal to the open circuit stiffness for small values of λ . When λ approaches to $-(1 - k_{31}^2)$ from positive small values, the effective modulus approaches positive infinity. However, when λ approaches to $-(1 - k_{31}^2)$ from large negative values, the effective modulus is changed from a positive value to a negative value, and eventually approaches negative infinity. The tunable modulus behavior of the shunted piezoelectric element will be used for the concept design of the active EMM.

Figure 1: Normalized effective modulus of piezoelectric patch with different NCRs.

2.2 Band gap control in an active EMM plate

A thin EMM plate with periodic cantilever-mass microstructures was proposed for low-frequency band gap applications [11]. In this section, we illustrate the practical application of how the periodic array of shunting piezoelectric patches bonded to the cantilever beam can function as the building block of an active EMM.

Figure 2 (a) shows the active EMM plate with a periodic array of cantilever-masses bonded by shunted piezoelectric patches. The detailed microstructure in the unit cell is shown in Fig. 2 (b). The plate behaves as a one-dimensional waveguide that supports the propagation of flexural waves. In the low-frequency range, the behaviors of micro-beams of resonators can be conveniently described through the Euler-Bernoulli theory with piecewise elastic and mass properties. The negative capacitance shunts are applied to piezoelectric patches installed in a periodic array, which consists of a series of equally spaced piezoelectric patches.

The thin plate beam is made of stainless steel ($E_s = 195$ GPa, $\rho_s = 8000$ kg / m³, $\nu_s = 0.33$) with thickness $t_s = 1$ mm and width $b_s = 0.45$ mm. The shunted piezoelectric materials are PZT-5H ($E_p = 60.6$ GPa, $\rho_p = 7500$ kg / m³, $\nu_p = 0.34$) with thickness $t_p = 0.1$ mm, length $l_p = 2.7$ mm and width $b_p = 0.45$ mm. The spacing of the adjacent unit cells is $a = 5.6$ mm.

Figure 3 shows the band gap variation (identified in the shaded regions) of the active EMM plate with surface-bonded piezoelectric patches with different NCRs $\lambda = -\frac{C_n}{C_p}$ for the out-of-plane bending wave. Figure 3 (a) shows the band gaps when $\lambda = 0$, i.e., the shunting circuits are open. In the figures,

ω_0 is the local resonance frequency of the cantilever resonator system with open circuit. The first band gap is in the range of $\omega = \omega_0 \sim 1.5\omega_0$. Figure 3 (b) shows the dispersion diagram and the first band gap of the EMM plate when $\lambda = -0.83$, in which the effective modulus of the shunted piezoelectric patch increases in a positive value, therefore the bending stiffness of the cantilever beam is increased. The width of the band gap is almost not changed, however, the frequency range of the first band gap is shifted from the original ($\omega_0 \sim 1.5\omega_0$) to ($1.13\omega_0 \sim 1.7\omega_0$). Figure 3 (c) shows dispersion diagram and the first band gap of the EMM plate when $\lambda = -0.842$, in which the effective stiffness of the shunted piezoelectric patch continuously increases in a positive value. The first band gap is shifted from the original band gap ($\omega_0 \sim 1.5\omega_0$) to ($1.19\omega_0 \sim 1.8\omega_0$). However, if the effective stiffness of the shunted piezoelectric patch continuously increases to a larger value, the local resonance is hard to be induced in the cantilever beam in the low-frequency range because of the finite stiffness in the host medium. Figure 3 (d) shows the band structure diagram of the EMM plate when $\lambda = -0.898$, in which the effective modulus of the shunted piezoelectric patch becomes a negative value, and therefore the effective bending stiffness of the cantilever beam is decreased. Comparing the band diagram with the open circuit, it is found that the band gap is shifted from the original band gap ($\omega_0 \sim 1.5\omega_0$) to ($0.62\omega_0 \sim 0.87\omega_0$). Figures 3 (e) and (f) show the band structure diagram of the EMM plate when $\lambda = -0.88$ and $\lambda = -0.8775$, respectively, in which the effective stiffness of the shunted piezoelectric patch is further reduced in a negative value. It is seen that the extremely low-frequency band gaps are located at the ranges of ($0.33\omega_0 \sim 0.42\omega_0$) and ($0.15\omega_0 \sim 0.19\omega_0$) for both cases. However, the width of the stop band becomes very narrow at the low-frequency cases for the bending wave. One important requirement to achieve the tunable band gap is to have the ability to adjust the value of the negative capacitance very accurately.

Figure 2: (a) Active elastic metamaterial plate with a periodic array of the cantilever-mass system bonded by shunted piezoelectric patches; (b) detailed microstructure in the unit cell.

Figure 3: Band gap variation of the active elastic metamaterial plate with different NCRs for out-of-plane bending wave, (a) $\lambda = 0$; (b) $\lambda = -0.83$; (c) $\lambda = -0.842$; (d) $\lambda = -0.898$; (e) $\lambda = -0.88$; (f) $\lambda = -0.8775$.

2.3 Conclusions

In this part, we investigated dispersion curves and band gap control in an active EMM plate with periodically surface-bonded piezoelectric patches which are shunted with a negative capacitive circuit. It is demonstrated that the location and the range of induced band gap of the active EMM plate can be effectively tuned by using shunted piezoelectric patches with different NCRs, especially for extremely low-frequency cases.

3 DIRECTIONAL CONTROL OF FLEXURAL WAVES IN ACTIVE EMMS WITH ER ELASTOMERS

The flexural waves in a plate have been extensively employed in structural health monitoring, thanks to their capability of long-range and through-the-thickness interrogation of structures [9,40,41]. To achieve high-resolution damage detection, controlling of flexural wave propagation paths is extremely essential in both emitting and receiving processes. For example, when a monitored object is not on the ray direction of the flexural wave propagation, a waveguide structure could steer the wave to a desired direction. Designing a waveguide device to achieve fully control of flexural waves would be of great benefit to the development of structural health monitoring and new sensors. In this part, we numerically demonstrate the design and physical realization of a flexural waveguide based on an active EMM with ER elastomers.

3.1 ER elastomers

ER elastomer is a kind of soft smart materials with shear modulus being controlled by applying an external magnetic/electric field [42]. Theoretically, the relation between dynamic shear modulus of the ER elastomer, G , and applied electric field of magnitude, \bar{E} , can be approximately expressed as [38,42]

$$G = G_0 \left[1 + \left(\bar{E} / E_0 \right)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

where G_0 is the shear modulus without electric field, and E_0 is a reference electric field. Based on Eq. (2), it can be concluded that the electric field has the ability to modify elastic properties, and thus may be used to control the dynamic behavior of the ER elastomer.

3.2 An active EMM for the flexural waveguide and focal lens

The unit cell design of the considered active EMM with tunable material parameter over a broad frequency range is schematically shown in Fig. 4, where an active resonator is equipped with an ER elastomer annulus sandwiched between an aluminum annular ring and an aluminum cylinder. The resonator is surface bonded on the top of the host plate. In the figure, a and h are the side length and the thickness of the unit lattice of the aluminum host plate. The radius and the height of the aluminum cylinder are denoted as r_c and h_c . The height and outer radiuses of the ER elastomer and aluminum annulus are represented by h_a , r_e and r_a , respectively.

Figure 4: Unit cell of the active EMM surface-bonded on the plate.

The working mechanism of the EMM can be briefly described as follows. When a bending wave propagates in the host plate with the surface-bonded EMM, the outer aluminum ring will be vibrated up and down with respect to the plate, and the ER elastomer will undergo shear-mode deformation. With the presence of the anti-resonant motion of the outer aluminum ring with respect to the host plate, the flexural wave energy is trapped in the resonator and an omnidirectional wave band gap will be observed, which can be interpreted by the negative effective mass density of the system [5]. In addition, the tunability and flexibility of the active EMM can be accomplished by tuning the shear modulus of the ER elastomer annulus under timely adjustable electric fields along the radial direction without altering the microstructures.

The numerically based effective medium method is used for determination of the out-of-plane effective mass density of the EMM [9,43]. Figure 5 shows the normalized effective mass densities of the proposed EMM under various magnitudes of applied electric fields by the finite element software, COMSOL Multiphysics. In the figure, ω_0 is the resonant frequency of the outer aluminum ring with $\bar{E} = 0$, and the microstructure dimensions and constitute material properties of the EMM are listed in Table 1.

As shown in the figure, the effective mass density reaches the positive infinity at the resonant frequency and immediately turns to the negative infinity, then gradually approaches to a positive constant value at higher frequencies. Negative effective mass densities (shaded areas) can be found near the resonant frequency, i.e. $\omega = \omega_0 \sim 1.3\omega_0$, when $\bar{E} = 0$. It can also be observed that the frequency

range of the negative effective mass density can be shifted by changing the magnitudes of applied electric fields. For example, when $\bar{E} = 2E_0, 4E_0$ and $8E_0$, the frequency range is shifted to $2.2\omega_0 \sim 2.8\omega_0, 3.9\omega_0 \sim 5.1\omega_0$ and $8.1\omega_0 \sim 9.8\omega_0$, respectively.

Figure 5: Effective mass density of the EMM under various magnitudes of electric fields.

It is understandable because the shear modulus of the ER elastomer is increased as the increase of the magnitude of electric field according to Eq. (2), which will result in the shift of the resonant frequency. It is also noticed that the frequency range of the negative effective mass density increases with the increase of the magnitude of the electric field. Finally, an extremely gradient distribution of effective mass density of the EMM can be accomplished by applying various magnitudes of electric fields at different frequencies. For example, as shown in the figure at $\omega = 3.9\omega_0$, the normalized effective mass density can be varied as 1.008, 0.7874, 7.555 and 1.758, respectively, when the electric field is tuned to be $\bar{E} = 0, 2E_0, 4E_0$ and $8E_0$, respectively, which provides a potential solution for wave steering lens devices. It should be mentioned that the tunability of the effective mass density through electric fields could be implemented very fast and in real time, which opens a new way for many practical applications of the active EMM.

Geometrical properties (in mm)		Material properties	
a	5	Mass density (Aluminum)	2700 kg/m ³
h	1.5	Lamé's first parameter (Aluminum)	51 GPa
ra	2	Shear modulus (Aluminum)	26 GPa
re	0.7	Mass density (ER elastomer)	1000 kg/m ³
rc	0.5	Lamé's first parameter (ER elastomer)	1532 KPa
ha	2	G0	64 KPa
hc	1.8	E0	1.3 kV/mm

Table 1. Unit cell geometrical and material parameters of the active EMM

3.3 The flexural waveguide with active EMMs

Up to that point, a flexural waveguide with a gradient material parameter profile can be readily made with an array of surface-bonded active EMMs. The tunability and flexibility of the waveguide will be discussed for the extraordinary wave steering over a broad frequency range.

Figure 6 (a) shows the schematic model of the flexural waveguide with an arbitrary steering angle β by the coordinate transformation method. According to the relations between material properties and principle stretches [43,44], there exist many options for material property selection of the transformed medium. For the ease of the physical realization, the relationship of the transformed medium and the host plate is selected as [43]

$$E' = E \quad (3a)$$

$$\rho' = \left(\frac{R_0}{r'} \right)^4 \rho \quad (3b)$$

where E' and ρ' are the Young's modulus and mass density of the transformed media, E and ρ are the Young's modulus and mass density of the host plate, r' is the transformed physical polar coordinate and R_0 is a constant.

As illustrated in the figure, an incident flexural wave beam is launched towards the designed waveguide, and the wave is then steered along the waveguide with a beam deflection angle β . Figure 6 (b) shows the physical realization of the waveguide by using an array of the proposed active EMMs with a 90° circular sector. The mass density profile of the waveguide from the transformation method will be approximately truncated by the discretely distributed EMMs under various electric fields. Applied electric fields are numerically determined through the wave dispersion analysis. For the array of EMMs with a 90° sector, as shown in Fig. 6 (b), the beam deflection angle β ($0^\circ < \beta < 90^\circ$) can be actively adjusted by properly selecting the controlled area of the EMM.

Figure 6: (a) Schematic of a flexural waveguide with a deflection angle β by the transformation method; (b) Physical realization of a flexural waveguide equipped with an array of active EMMs.

Figure 7 shows the out-of-plane wave field of the flexural waveguide with the deflection angle being 90° based on the transformed material parameters (Eq. (3)) at the frequencies of 15 kHz, 30 kHz and 50 kHz, respectively. In the model, perfectly-matched-layers (PMLs) on the host plate are adopted to simulate infinite boundaries for flexural wave propagation. The material parameters of the host plate are the same as those listed in Table 1. The waveguide is designed with the inner and outer radii of the circular sector being 10 mm and 100 mm, respectively. A harmonic antisymmetric Gaussian displacement profile is launched along the left edge of the plate. It can be observed that the direction of flexural waves can almost be deflected into 90° for different frequencies. Small reflections are found on the interfaces between the waveguide and the background plate, due to the material mismatch between the host medium and transformed medium. In addition, scattered waves in the host plate leaking from the waveguide are also observed, which is caused by the width expansion of Gaussian beam. Specifically, when the incident frequency is increased from 15 kHz to 50 kHz, the scattered wave becomes nearly invisible.

For the physical realization of the waveguide, an array of active EMMs is proposed. Figure 8 shows the numerical demonstration of the flexural waveguide by using the active EMM at different operating frequencies of 15 kHz, 30 kHz and 50 kHz, respectively. For the active EMM, the outer radius of the aluminum ring r_a is selected as 0.9 mm, and other geometrical and material parameters are the same as those used in Fig. 8. In the simulation, the required mass density profiles at different frequencies are approximated by the discretely distributed EMM through actively adjusting the applied electric field on the ER elastomer without altering the microstructure. It can be found that flexural waves are indeed steered into 90° as desired at all frequencies. Very good agreement with results predicted from the transformation method is observed, which shows the feasibility of the proposed active EMM. It is noticed that interior scattering waves within the discretely distributed EMM nearly vanish because of

the unique subwavelength feature of the proposed EMM compared with the wavelength of the operating frequency in the host plate.

Figure 7: Normalized out-of-plane wave field of a 90° flexural waveguide with material parameters from transformation method at different incident frequencies: (a) 15 kHz; (b) 30 kHz; (c) 50 kHz.

Figure 8: Normalized out-of-plane wave field of a 90° flexural waveguide equipped with an array of active EMMs at different incident frequencies: (a) 15 kHz; (b) 30 kHz; (c) 50 kHz.

Figure 9 shows the out-of-plane wave field of the flexural waveguide based on the proposed EMM at the operating frequency 15 kHz with the deflection angle being 15, 45, 60°, respectively. In the simulation, material and geometrical parameters of the active EMM are the same as those used in Fig. 8. As illustrated in the figure, the deflection angle can be flexibly tuned by applying electric fields on the selected areas (shaded areas) of the active EMM without altering the microstructures. The implied wave mechanism is that the effective mass density in the unselected area of the EMM is close to the mass density of the host plate at the operating frequency, therefore, effects on the flexural wave propagation due to the bonded EMM can be ignored.

Figure 9: Normalized out-of-plane wave field of the flexural waveguide with controlled active EMMs at the operating frequency 15 kHz with various deflection angles: (a) 15°; (b) 45°; (c) 60°.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, two types of active EMMs with shunted piezoelectric materials and electrorheological elastomers are suggested. Theoretical analyses and numerical validations of the active EMMs with detailed microstructures are presented for designing adaptive applications in band gap structures and extraordinary waveguides by adjusting circuit element parameters and applied electric fields without altering the microstructures. This new concept and technology should lead to new relevant applications for noise and/or vibration control, integrated surface actuators or micro-acousto-optic devices for adaptive applications in telecommunications and health monitoring of structures.

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